

УДК 338.2(476)+316.42(476)
JEL Classification: H10, J58, P35, Z13

THE SYSTEM OF ENSURING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SECURITY OF THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR

©*Shvaiba D.*, ORCID: 0000-0001-6783-9765, Ph.D.,
Minsk regional organization of the Belarusian Trade Union of workers of chemical,
mining and oil industries; Belarusian national technical University,
Minsk, Belarus, shvabia@tut.by

СИСТЕМА ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО СЕКТОРА

©*Швайба Д. Н.*, ORCID: 0000-0001-6783-9765, канд. экон. наук,
Минская областная организация Белорусского профсоюза работников химической,
горной и нефтяной отраслей промышленности;
Белорусский национальный технический университет, г. Минск, Беларусь, shvabia@tut.by

Abstract. The methodological basis for the formation of the system of ensuring socio-economic security includes features of the industrial sector. The specifics of his defense was designed to show with the help of the methodological and operational foundations. Methodological framework is formulated based on the research process the functional specificity provide socio-economic security of the industrial sector. They form the perimeter of ensuring social and economic security, which is formed by the expectations of society from the defense system of the industrial sector of the country. Operating bases are complementary to the functional specificity of the system provide socio-economic security by means of the formation of a specific institutional framework. Among them, the following are noted: modeling, allowing multivariate escalation of adverse events in the industrial sector and methods of its evaluation; instrumental assistance, taking into account the need for instrumental diversity for the implementation of defense functions in changing criteria (the environment of the industrial sector, its structure and the state of inter-element connections); functional coherence as the need to balance the goals of ensuring the socio-economic security of the industrial sector with the objectives and values of the formation of the industrial sector of the country, which are fixed in the policy documents of the state.

Аннотация. Методологические основы формирования системы обеспечения социально-экономической безопасности предусматривают особенности промышленного сектора. Специфику его защиты предлагается отобразить при помощи методических и операционных основ. Методические основы сформулированы исходя из поставленной исследовательским процессом функциональной специфичности обеспечения социально-экономической безопасности промышленного сектора. Они образуют периметр обеспечения социально-экономической безопасности, который формируется ожиданиями общества от системы обороны промышленного сектора страны. Операционные основы дополняют функциональную специфику системы обеспечения социально-экономической безопасности при помощи формирования определенной организационной базы. Среди них отмечены следующие: моделирования, допускающего многовариантность эскалации неблагоприятных явлений в промышленном секторе и методик ее оценки; инструментальной помощи, учитывающего надобность инструментального многообразия для реализации

функций обороны в изменяющихся критериях (среды функционирования промышленного сектора, его структуры и состояния межэлементных связей); функциональной согласованности как потребности соотношения целей обеспечения социально-экономической безопасности промышленного сектора задачам и ценностям становления промышленного сектора страны, которые зафиксированы в программных документах государства.

Keywords: socio-economic security; the government; society; enterprise; employee; threat; security; interests; Economics, analysis, system.

Ключевые слова: социально-экономическая защищенность; государство; общество; предприятие; работник; угроза; защищенность; интересы; экономика, анализ, система.

In General, the methodology for the formation of the system of ensuring the socio-economic security of the industrial sector involves the formulation of the foundations that reflect its system qualities and features of the criteria for operation. The results of the study of the problem showed that the necessary for the corresponding system structure of the basis makes sense to carry out in accordance with their priority: methodological (General) — methodical (special) — operational (specialized). The proposed bases are formulated on the basis of the analysis of provisions of legislative acts [1; 2]. The purpose and content of the bases are displayed in a number of sources [3; 4; 5]. The methodological basis is considered fundamental and formulated in accordance with the generalized qualities of the systems, taking into account the object of the industrial sector. Their implementation in the system of social and economic security allows to give it structural certainty. The content of the total (methodological) basis is established on the basis of the study of the qualities of the industrial sector as a economic system and its object identification. The result of the use of methodological, methodical and operational bases in relation to the specificity of the industrial sector is presented in the following conceptual structure of this system (Figure 1.).

The formulated basis is aimed at giving the system the proper qualities. First and foremost, the property of emergentist, which guarantees the imperative of security of the state socio-economic interests. In-2, diversity, the need for which comes from the individuality of the multi-aspect structure of the industrial sector and the plurality of varieties of activity in its environment. Third, self-referential (operational) isolation, due to the systemic integrity of the industrial sector and its ability to operate relatively autonomously. This is expressed by the data of financial and economic independence. But a certain share of resource and monetary provision of functional capacity is formed by means of the mechanism of interaction with the external environment. The better the interaction, the more likely the emergence of financial and economic dependence. Thus, the principle of self-referent closure reflects 1 part of the assessment of the circumstances of the steady development of the industrial complex—the symmetry of the interpretation of external and internal processes — "dependence–independence". Fourth, the property of a reflexive "loop", which provides the reactivity of the industrial sector to the dangers and the way of spreading the adverse impact in the areas related to the production [6; 7].

The methodological basis for the formation of the system of social and economic security provide for the features of the industrial sector. The specifics of his defense was designed to show with the help of the methodological and operational foundations. The methodical bases are formulated on the basis of the functional specificity of providing social and economic security of the industrial sector, set by the research process. They form the perimeter of social and economic

security, which is formed by the expectations of society from the defense system of the industrial sector of the country.

Figure. The scheme of the conceptual structure of the system of socio-economic security of the industrial sector. *Source:* elaboration of author.

To begin with, the principle of effectiveness. It implies the assessment of the prevented harm (direct effect) in case the option of elimination of the results of the manifested danger with a minimum amount of expenses of the company (indirect effect) has been implemented and the stability of functioning (implicit effect) can be achieved. In-2, the principle of adequacy, reflecting the ratio of methods of protection of the industrial sector the results of level measurements of socio-economic security in relation to the current period. B-3, complexity, allowing the functional probability of simultaneous protection of essential (system) components of the industrial sector and its segmental control (control of the state and formation of the leading parts of the structure). B-4-x, accounting for limited maneuverability, providing for the entry of restrictions (limits) of the defense of the industrial sector, due to the need for public spending on this protection. B-5-x, accounting for the incompleteness of the information array, as an important principle to display the complexities of the environment of the industrial sector. B-6, taking into accounts the form of relations of inter-subject interests, which allows for all kinds of States of personalized interests in the process of their implementation, but it is expected that only the conflict of interests should be considered as a subjective danger of the industrial sector.

The operational framework complements the functional specificity of the system of socio-economic security through the formation of a certain organizational base. Among them are the following: modeling, allowing the multivariance of the escalation of adverse events in the industrial sector and methods of its assessment; instrumental assistance, taking into account the need for instrumental diversity for the implementation of defense functions in changing criteria (environment of the industrial sector, its structure and state of interelement relations); functional coherence as a need to balance the goals of ensuring socio-economic security of the industrial sector and the objectives of the values of the industrial sector of the country, which are fixed in the policy documents of the state.

The conceptual structure of the system of ensuring socio-economic security of the industrial sector, shown in Figure, it is set on the basis of the provisions of the above methodological principles of management of objects of protection and evolutionary nature of protection in accordance with the proper motivational setting: to give the created system organizational unity and active capacity. The individuality of the proposed conceptual structure is as follows. Because of the division of the blocks of structuring and functioning, the structure of the system is conceived taking into account the difference of tasks — to help the stability of the structure and its functionality. The question of the subject composition ensuring the security of the industrial sector was studied by the method of decomposition of the active system of social, economic and industrial security of the Republic of Belarus [8; 9]. The study revealed the limitations of the elemental composition. In particular, it does not integrate special types of activities (processes) that accompany the implementation of state interests. But just they provide the implementation of transformational processes that appear as a result of the manifestation of destabilizing moments. It means that it will be necessary to review the element basis of the system of ensuring the socio-economic security of the industrial sector in accordance with the needs of the changed environment of its functioning. For the destruction of the discovered defect, a subsequent approach is proposed. It makes sense to divide the elemental composition not only by the symptom of the status property of the subjects, but also by the content of the types of works that create the interelement bonds necessary for the formation of the "strength threshold". Their ordered array allows to preserve the stability of the structure in situations of destabilizing influence. The point is that the variety of varieties of purposeful work can guarantee the management of modification along the chain of interelement relations and the preparation of an updated structure taking into account the claims of changed circumstances.

To form a protection system capable of supporting the internal capacity of the industrial sector to counter threats without direct intervention of state bodies, it is proposed to foresee a number of provisions. The functional base of the system is ready to set the joint basis used in the development of difficult systems: manageability and focus. Thus, the principle of purposefulness is applied to highlight the guidelines for the provision of socio-economic security, which are set by higher-level systems and emerging external criteria. In coordination with the above, such guidelines as national interests, universal values and priority socio-economic interests are indicated. The principle of maneuverability provided by cybernetic and system-situational approaches assumes the exact organization of interaction of industrial sector with system of providing its social and economic security and with financial and economic system of the state. To implement this circumstance, a block of socio-economic security forecast is proposed, which is created to "monitor" the state and formation of the industrial sector by the characteristics of its functioning with respect to the tasks of the defense of state interests. As shown in the diagram, to give the system of ensuring the socio-economic security of the industrial sector sufficient functionality, a suitable mechanism is taken into account. In this case, the necessary condition for the formation of an effective mechanism is the preservation of continuity with a previously formed and active mechanism.

Thus, in the aggregate, the proposed foundations, the logic of structuring and functioning, as well as interaction with external security systems form the methodological basis of the system of ensuring the socio-economic security of the industrial sector.

References:

1. Senko, A. N. (2002). Problems of Measuring the Economic Security of the Country. Public Administration: *Transformation Processes in the Modern World: Math. Intern. scientific-practical. Conf., Minsk, January 29-30. 2002: at 2 pm Minsk, (1). 140-142.*
2. Senko, A. N. (2003). Economic interests in the mechanism of the self-development of the nation and the problems of their protection. *Demography and safety of life: materials Mezhdunar. Congress, Minsk, 14-15 November. 2002. Intern. Institute of Labor and Social. relations; rare: N. Ye. Potapenko (editor of the editorial board). Minsk, 180-182.*
3. Babosov, E. M. (2006). Sociology of personality, stratification and control. Minsk: *Belarusian Science, 590.*
4. Geyzler, P. S., & Zavyalova, O. V. (2005). Project management. Minsk: *Belarusian State Economic University, 255.*
5. Gradov, A. P. (2001). Economic security of the country and priorities of investment policy. *Economic science of modern Russia, (3). 70-78.*
6. Shvayba, D. N. Problems of the coordination of goals and vital interests while ensuring social and economic security. *Nauka i Tekhnika. DOI: 10.21122/2227-1031-2017-16-6-526-531*
7. Shvaiba, D. N. (2017). Analysis of the components of socio-economic security. *Problems of management, 3 (65). 96-102.*
8. Senko, A. N. (2004). Economic Security of the Industrial Complex. Minsk: *Law and Economics, 225.*
9. Senko, A. N. (2005). Formation of the system for ensuring the economic security of the industrial complex of the Republic of Belarus. Minsk: *Law and Economics, 114.*

Список литературы:

1. Сенько А. Н. Проблемы измерения экономической безопасности страны // Государственное управление: трансформационные процессы в современном мире: мат. Междунар. науч.-практ. конф., Минск, 29–30 янв. 2002 г.: в 2 ч. Минск, 2002. Ч. 1. С. 140–142.

2. Сенько А. Н. Экономические интересы в механизме саморазвития нации и проблемы их защиты // Проблемы демографии и безопасности жизни: материалы Междунар. конгр., Минск, 14–15 нояб. 2002 г. Междунар. ин-т трудовых и соц. отношений; редкол.: Н. Е. Потапенко (отв. ред.). Минск, 2003. С. 180–182.

3. Бабосов Е. М. Социология личности, стратификации и управления. Минск: Белорусская наука, 2006. 590 с.

4. Гейзлер П. С., Завьялова О. В. Управление проектами. Минск: Белорусский государственный экономический университет, 2005. 255 с.

5. Градов А. П. Экономическая безопасность страны и приоритеты инвестиционной политики // Экономическая наука современной России. 2001. № 3. С. 70–78.

6. Швайба Д. Н. Проблемы согласования целей и жизненных интересов при обеспечении социально-экономической безопасности // Наука и техника. DOI: 10.21122/2227-1031-2017-16-6-526-531

7. Швайба Д. Н. Анализ составляющих социально-экономической безопасности // Проблемы управления. 2017. № 3 (65). С. 96–102.

8. Сенько А. Н. Экономическая безопасность промышленного комплекса. Минск: Право и экономика, 2004. 225 с.

9. Сенько А. Н. Формирование системы обеспечения экономической безопасности промышленного комплекса Республики Беларусь. Минск: Право и экономика, 2005. 114 с.

*Работа поступила
в редакцию 26.05.2018 г.*

*Принята к публикации
02.06.2018 г.*

Cite as (APA):

Shvaiba, D. (2018). The system of ensuring social and economic security of the industrial sector. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 4(7), 227-232.

Ссылка для цитирования:

Shvaiba D. The system of ensuring social and economic security of the industrial sector // Бюллетень науки и практики. 2018. Т. 4. №7. С. 227-232. Режим доступа: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/d-shvaiba> (дата обращения 15.07.2018).